

Nassarius acer n. sp., a new species of Nassariidae (Gastropoda, Neogastropoda) from Indo-Western Pacific

Nassarius acer n. sp., una nueva especie de Nassariidae (Gastropoda, Neogastropoda) del Indopacífico Occidental

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ABSTRACT

A new species of the genus *Nassarius*, *N. acer* n. sp., from Indonesia is described. Although uncommon, specimens with this morphology were known but had never been formally described as a new species. This new species is compared with other species of the same genus of similar appearance.

RESUMEN

Se describe una nueva especie del género *Nassarius*, *N. acer* n. sp., de Indonesia. A pesar de ser poco comunes, especímenes con esta morfología eran conocidos pero nunca se habían descrito formalmente como especie nueva. Esta nueva especie se compara con otras especies del mismo género de aspecto similar.

KEY WORDS: Gastropoda, Nassariidae, *Nassarius*, new species, Indonesia.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Gastropoda, Nassariidae, *Nassarius*, nueva especie, Indonesia.

INTRODUCTION

The family Nassariidae, especially the genus *Nassarius* Dumeril, 1805, has a large diversity of species in Indonesian islands waters, similar to that found in the Philippines. Most of these species were described in the classical literature but, recently, specimens have been obtained in this area showing a shell morphology quite different from of any other species of *Nassarius* described before. They are quite large for the genus, around 28 mm, have a tall and

very sharp spire, and fine and very dense sculpture in the first whorls.

Such specimens, although they are not common, were already known but were never formally described in the literature. On the Conchology Inc. website <<https://www.conchology.be/>>, in its Encyclopedia page, there are images that match this morphology labelled as "*Nassarius* species" and are detailed herein (see "Other material studied").

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Based on the specimens showing the abovementioned morphology, collected in Indonesia, a new species is proposed under the name *Nassarius acer* n. sp.; and is compared with other *Nassarius* species of similar characters.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material studied was obtained from Indonesian suppliers, who obtain them from fishermen. All this material, with the exception of the holotype, is part of the author's personal collection. The

specimens have been studied under the stereomicroscope, and measurements were taken with a digital calliper adjusting the values to the tenth of a millimetre or, in the case of protoconchs, with a micrometric ocular in the stereomicroscope. Photographs were taken with a NIKON Coolpix 5700 digital camera.

Abbreviations:

CG: Carles Gili collection, Barcelona, Spain.

MZB: Museu de Ciències Naturals de Barcelona collection, Barcelona, Spain.

SYSTEMATIC PART

Superfamily BUCCINOIDEA Rafinesque, 1815

Family NASSARIIDAE Iredale, 1916 (1835)

Subfamily NASSARIINAE Iredale, 1916 (1835)

Genus *Nassarius* Duméril, 1805

Type species *Buccinum arcularia* Linnaeus, 1758 (by subsequent monotypy, Frieriep, 1806).
Recent.

Nassarius acer n. sp. (Figs. 1, 2)

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Type material. Holotype: INDONESIA • 1 shell (height 27.5 mm, maximum diameter 11.4 mm, Fig. 1 A-D); Sumbawa Island, Labuan Bajo; leg. R. Wardana; MZB 2024-3813. Paratypes: INDONESIA • 7 shells; same locality as the holotype; leg. R. Wardana, A. Setiawan & Kusairi; CG 2872-N.

Other material: 1 shell from unknown locality, CG 2408-N; images of 6 shells (Fig. 2) posted on the Conchology Inc. website (© Guido & Philippe Poppe <www.conchology.be> (Encyclopedia): "species 014", num. 210484 from Philippines and num. 305740 from Australia; "species 032", num. 716747 and num. 855476 both from Philippines; "species 108", num. 948567, from Philippines; and "species 110", num. 513799 from Philippines, with shell height 26.5 to 30.9 mm, obtained at depths between 50 and 150 m.

Type locality: Indonesia, Sumbawa Island, off Labuan Bajo. There is some uncertainty about the origin of the material studied, it could also have been obtained somewhere NW of Sumbawa such Lombok or Flores.

Etymology: From Latin acer-acris-acre meaning sharp, pointed, in reference to the acute shape of the spire.

Description: Shell narrow, with a very acute spire and linear suture, with fine axial ribs and spiral cords on the first whorls. The diameter of the last whorl represents about 44% and the spire about 59%, both with respect to the total height.

The protoconch has 3 – 3.5 whorls (including nucleus), the last two carinate, the exposed part about 0.96 mm wide and 0.80 mm high, terminated by a concave scar (opisthocytic). The teleoconch has 7.5 – 8 whorls. Teleoconch sculpture starts with fine axial ribs and

Figure 1. *Nassarius acer* n. sp. A-D: holotype, Indonesia, Sumbawa, Labuan Bajo (height 27.5 mm), MZB 2024-3813 (ex CG 2872-N). E-F: shell from unknown locality (height 35.6 mm), CG 2408-N. G-I: paratype, Indonesia, Sumbawa, Labuan Bajo (height 24.3 mm), CG 2872-N. J: operculum of a paratype, Indonesia, Sumbawa, Labuan Bajo, CG 2872-N.

Figura 1. *Nassarius acer* n. sp. A-D: *holotipo*, Indonesia, Sumbawa, Labuan Bajo (altura 27,5 mm), MZB 2024-3813 (ex CG 2872-N). E-F: *concha de una localidad desconocida* (altura 35,6 mm), CG 2408-N. G-I: *paratipo*, Indonesia, Sumbawa, Labuan Bajo (altura 24,3 mm), CG 2872-N. J: *opérculo de un paratipo*, Indonesia, Sumbawa, Labuan Bajo, CG 2872-N.

Figure 2. Images of *Nassarius acer* n. sp. posted on the Conchology Inc. website at the time of this publication. A: “species 014”, from the Philippines (height 29.9 mm), num. 210484; B: “species 032”, from the Philippines (height 26.5 mm), num. 716747; C, D: “species 032”, from the Philippines (height 30.6 mm), num. 855476; E, F: “species 108” from the Philippines (height 28.0 mm), num. 948567; G: “species 110” from the Philippines (height 30.9 mm), num. 513799; H: “species 014”, from Australia (height 30.0 mm), num. 305740. Images © Guido & Philippe Poppe <www.conchology.be>.

Figura 2. Imágenes de *Nassarius acer* n. sp. publicadas en el sitio web de Conchology Inc. al momento de esta publicación. A: “especie 014”, de Filipinas (altura 29,9 mm), núm. 210484; B: “especie 032”, de Filipinas (altura 26,5 mm), núm. 716747; C, D: “especie 032”, de Filipinas (altura 30,6 mm), núm. 855476; E, F: “especie 108” de Filipinas (altura 28,0 mm), núm. 948567; G: “especie 110” de Filipinas (altura 30,9 mm), núm. 513799; H: “especie 014”, de Australia (altura 30,0 mm), núm. 305740. Imágenes © Guido & Philippe Poppe <www.conchology.be>.

spiral cords forming slight granulations at their intersection. The ribs are very closely set, about 30 per whorl, gradu-

ally fading away until they disappear completely from the penultimate whorl onward. On early teleoconch whorls,

there are 7 – 8 spiral cords separated by shallow and narrow grooves, initially high, then becoming flat, and gradually disappearing towards the aperture. Two finely granulated subsutural spiral cords persist on the penultimate whorl, and only one on the last whorl which extends to the outer lip. There are 3 – 4 spiral cords at the base of the shell, and 6 – 7 more on the siphonal canal externally. Aperture elliptical to rather rounded, with very shallow inner denticles. Outer lip regularly convex, with 4 – 5 basal spines on the edge. External varix narrow and hardly raised. Columella regularly concave, smooth, with a slight parietal denticle. Columellar callus bordering the columella, slightly

detached and not expanding. Operculum corneous, elliptical (Fig. 1J).

Colour background ochre with three poorly defined brown bands, one subsutural, one in the middle and one at the base of the last whorl. An irregular dorsal spot present on the body whorl that often develops as a few vertical stripes.

Distribution and habitat: All the studied specimens, except one of unknown locality, are from Indonesia, Sumbawa Island, Labuan Bajo. The images of shells on the Conchology website show that the new species is also found in the Philippines and Australia. No depth data are known for the studied material, for the Conchology specimens 50 – 150 m is indicated.

DISCUSSION

The material studied as a whole is morphologically very homogeneous. The number of teleoconch whorls varies between 7.5 – 8, and the adult shell length between 25.6 – 30.4 mm. The number of axial ribs and spiral cords varies slightly, and the extension of the ribs can reach the penultimate whorl (Fig. 1 G-I). The internal denticles of the outer lip presents more variations, they can be absent, or 5 – 6 in the abapical half, or occupying all the internal part of the outer lip. The specimen studied from unknown locality (Fig. 1 E-F) is deviating because it has 8.75 teleoconch whorls and has a length of 35.6 mm, this is larger than the type specimens and has a much more rounded outer lip.

Nassarius acer n. sp. could be confused with some species of similar morphology treated by CERNOHORSKY (1984: 146, Pl. 29) as synonyms of *Nassarius comptus* (A. Adams, 1852), a very heterogeneous grouping. These are *Nassarius excellens* (Kuroda & Habe, 1961), *Nassarius tateyamensis* (Kuroda, 1929), *Nassarius politus* (Marrat, 1880) and *Nassarius cinnamomeus* (A. Adams, 1852), which are considered valid species and different from *N. comptus* by several authors (DRIVAS & JAY, 1988; KASE & KINJO, 1996;

HIGO ET AL., 1999; TSUCHIYA IN OKUTANI, 2000; ROBIN, 2008; DEKKER & DEKKERS, 2009; BOUTET ET AL., 2020). All these species have elongated shells, with some thick axial ribs and spiral cords on the first teleoconch whorls and becoming smooth on the last whorls. However, none of them have such fine and numerous ribs, nor such fine cords in the first whorls, and neither the granular subsutural cord as *N. acer* n. sp.

STURANY (1900) described a Red Sea species, *Nassarius steindachneri* (Sturany, 1900) quite similar in profile, ornamentation and size. It is considered, in my opinion erroneously, synonymous with *Nassarius thumasius* (Sturany, 1900) by SINGER & MIENIS (1997), DEKKER & ORLIN (2000), VAN GEMERT (2006) and ALBANO ET AL. (2017). However *Nassarius steindachneri* has numerous, narrow, slightly curved ribs and very narrow ridges all over the shell, and the aperture is more elongated, as can be seen in SINGER & MIENIS (1997) or ALBANO ET AL. (2017: fig. 15A-G). *Nassarius poupini* Cernohorsky, 1992 has also a similar profile and size but has a narrower shell, only a few thick axial ribs on the first teleoconch whorls and shows a more elongated aperture (CERNOHORSKY, 1992).

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ALBANO P.G., BAKKER P.A.J., JANSSEN R. & ESCHNER A. 2017. An illustrated catalogue of Rudolf Sturany's type specimens in the Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Austria (NHMW): Red Sea Gastropods. *Zoosystematics and Evolution*, 93 (1), 45-94.
- BOUTET M., GOURGUET, R & LETOURNEUX J. 2020. *Mollusques marins de Polynésie française / Marine molluscs of French Polynesia*. Au vent des îles, Pirae. 766 pp.
- CERNOHORSKY W.O. 1984. Systematics of the family Nassariidae (Mollusca: Gastropoda). *Bulletin of the Auckland Institute and Museum*, 14, 1-356.
- CERNOHORSKY, W.O. 1992. Description of new species of Nassariidae (Mollusca, Neogastropoda) from the Pacific Ocean. *Bulletin du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris*, 4 ser., 14 (A, 1), 69-74.
- C O N C H O L O G Y .
<https://www.conchology.be/?t=4042&family=NASSARIIDAE>. Last accessed September, 15, 2024.
- DEKKER H. & DEKKERS A.M. 2009. A new species, *Nassarius kooli* n. sp. (Gastropoda: Nassariidae), from deep water in the Philippines and Japan. *Miscellanea Malacologica*, 3 (6), 117-120.
- DEKKER H. & ORLIN Z. 2000. Check-list of Red Sea Mollusca. *Spirula*, 47 (suppl.), 1-47.
- DRIVAS J. & JAY M. 1988. *Coquillages de La Réunion et de l'île Maurice*. Les Editions du Pacifique, Singapore. 159 pp.
- HIGO S., CALLOMON P. & GOTO Y. 1999. *Catalogue and bibliography of the marine shell-bearing Mollusca of Japan*. Elle Scientific Publications, Osaka-fu. 938 pp.
- KASE T. & KINJO H. 1996. A nassariid gastropod from the submarine caves of Okinawa, Japan and Bohol, Philippines: Taxonomic status of *Nassa cinnamomea* A. Adams, 1852. *Venus* 55 (3): 199-205.
- OKUTANI T. 2000. *Marine mollusks in Japan*. Tokai University Press, Tokyo. 1173 pp.
- ROBIN A. 2008. *Encyclopedia of marine gastropods*. AFC-Xenophora & Conchbooks, Paris & Hackenheim. 480 pp.
- SINGER B.S. & MIENIS H.K. 1997. The family Nassariidae of the Red Sea, part II. *La Conchiglia* 29 (283): 36-43.
- STURANY R. 1900. Diagnosen neuer Gastropoden aus dem Rothen Meer als Vorlauffer einer Bearbeitung dem gesammten, von S. M. Schiff "Pola" gefundenen Gastropoden. *Anzeige der Kaiserlichen Akademie der Wissenschaften, Mathematisch-Naturwissenschaftliche Classe*, 17, 197-201.
- VAN GEMERT L.J. 2006. The Nassariidae of the Red Sea, a review of the literature with remarks on their distribution in the western part of the Indian Ocean and report of own findings. *De Kreukel*, 42 (4-5), 47-88.

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